

Development and acceptability of healthy baked products using arrowroot flour

Joila Marie L. Gonzales, Hannah Shane P. Mariano

Abstract

The purpose of this study is to see how effective arrowroot flour is for the development and acceptance of developing a healthy baked goods, particularly Arrowroot Pandesal. The purpose of this research is to find the significant differences between Arrowroot pandesal and traditional or local pandesal. It was rated on a 7-point hedonic scale based on sensory aspects such as appearance, aroma, texture, taste, color, and overall acceptability. The researchers also wanted to see if there was a significant difference in the evaluations. This study aims to develop a healthy baked food utilizing arrowroot flour and test its acceptability rate through experimental research. The researcher considered having two types of respondents: Trained Personnel and Expert Personnel. Both groups were credible and knowledgeable about the study. Our research instrument was a survey questionnaire, which was examined using the mean score, T-test, and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). This research aims to develop and introduce goods not just for the culinary sector, but also for the general public. There was no significant difference in sensory evaluation between the arrowroot pandesal and the traditional pandesal, according to the results. The data indicates and proves that the sensory qualities of arrowroot and traditional pandesal are not very different. The majority of the scores were slightly to moderately satisfactory. Apart from the findings of this investigation, the researchers also observed that arrowroot pandesal cannot be made using arrowroot flour on its own as a fundamental ingredient. The following recommendations are based on the above findings and conclusions: undertake a larger-scale population survey for better and more credible results. Lastly, improvement on the sensory characteristics of the arrowroot pandesal itself.

Keywords: Development; Acceptability; Healthy baked products; Arrowroot flour.

Joila Marie L. Gonzales*

Hannah Shane P. Mariano

Hospitality Management Department, St. Dominic College of Asia, Bacoor City, Cavite, Philippines

*Corresponding author

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Introduction

Arrowroot powder is used as a highly processed form of starch. It is commonly used as flour for other baked products and somehow gives us a high level of health benefits. According to different blog sites and pages, arrowroot can produce a high-quality and newly introduced product as compared to other thickening agents and flour.

It is a low-perennial herb observed in rainforest habitats. It can develop to approximately 2 ft excessive and has small white vegetation and fruits. Arrowroot is fabricated from the West Indies, which has a wealthy records within the lifestyle that its very call arrowroot changed into derived from the indigenous tribe of Arawaks. According to historians, Arawak humans used arrowroot powder to attract out toxic pollutants from the ones wounded via way of means of the guidelines of poisoned arrows. Arrowroot is indigenous in tropical America but has spread to other countries such as Brazil, India, Ceylon, Indonesia, and the Philippines. Arrowroot was first introduced in the Philippines in 1918. In general, arrowroots have thick, fleshy, large leaves, and the creeping roots are long and fibrous. Flour is almost the same as cornstarch: white, fine, and powdery. Arrowroot powder is a healthier alternative. It is the only starch product that contains calcium ash, which is important for maintaining the proper balance of acid and base in the human body. It is a tough plant that thrives as long as there is sufficient soil moisture for growth and development. Crops grow best in places where rainfall is evenly distributed throughout the year. Moreover, arrowroot tubers can be an effective substitute for corn in broiler rations and are considered to be excellent roughage for animal feeds. The fibrous by-product can also be used to feed cattle and swine, while the leaves can be used as a packaging material.

Arrowroot is a very versatile plant. It has a lot of benefits for our health and for the culinary industry. This research focused on the process of making flour or starch from the plant. Arrowroot flour is inherently gluten-free, works well as a thickening ingredient in puddings, sauces, and stews, and may also be used as a binder in meatloaf and veggie burger combinations. Arrowroot may aid in the prevention of birth defects, the promotion of appropriate growth and development, and the improvement of circulation, blood pressure, weight, and digestion. The use of this starch is not only limited to the culinary industry itself, but it also has a lot of benefits for our bodies. It is also good for digestion, heart health, fighting the salmonella virus, skin care, and weight loss.

According to Alfaro (2020), arrowroot is a type of starch obtained from the root of a tropical plant that grows in tropical climates. Arrowroot is a thickening agent for soups and sauces that is processed into a white powder. Despite the distinctions, arrowroot and cornstarch are occasionally used interchangeably. Arrowroot should not be used with dairy products since the texture will be unpleasant. Based on the statement, it can be produced with high quality carbohydrates, which are usually considered as staple foods. Through this literature, the researchers aim to produce a high quality, effective and efficient staple food from arrowroot flour.

Statement of the Problem

This study was conducted to develop baked products using arrowroot flour. Specifically, the following statements are the questions that should be answered after the study takes place:

1. What are the sensory characteristics of the developed baked product (pandesal) using arrowroot flour in terms of the following:
 - 1.1. General appearance,
 - 1.2. Color,
 - 1.3. Aroma,
 - 1.4. Texture, and
 - 1.5. Taste?
2. Is there a significant difference in the sensory characteristics of the developed pandesal prepared using arrowroot flour compared to the Traditional Pandesal?
3. Is there a significant difference in the ratings of the two groups of panelists such as: a) trained panelists (culinary instructors), and b) experts (chefs) with regard to sensory characteristics and overall acceptability of the developed pandesal prepared with arrowroot flour?

The output was evaluated through these statements by the two sets of panelists. Trained Laboratory Panel, which composed of the four (4) faculty members from St. Dominic College of Asia, Cavite was invited to participate in the sensory evaluation of food samples. They were classified as "trained laboratory panels" that has specific sensory capabilities, which might be skilled so as to take part as a respondent for this research. The other set of panelists was considered as the Expert Sensory Panel. Five chefs in Cavite were chosen as the expert sensory panel. The chefs served as the expert sensory panel in the panel since it was assumed that they had greater formal training to have a credible analysis and evaluation of the arrowroot pandesal considering its sensory characteristics and overall acceptability as compared with traditional pandesal.

Hypothesis

To answer the objectives of this study, the hypotheses that were tested are:

- H1. There is no significant difference between the sensory characteristics of the developed arrowroot pandesal prepared with arrowroot flour and the traditional pandesal.
- H2. There is no significant difference between the overall acceptability of the developed arrowroot pandesal prepared with arrowroot flour and the traditional pandesal.
- H3. There is no significant difference in the ratings of the two groups of panelists such as: a) trained panelists (culinary instructors), and b) experts (chefs) with regard to sensory characteristics and overall acceptability of the developed arrowroot pandesal prepared with arrowroot flour.

Significance of the Study

The outcome of this study would introduce arrowroot pandesal made from arrowroot. As researchers, they would like to introduce a new high quality product and showcase the different factors that this arrowroot has.

The result of the experiment served as a basis and proof on how this flour could be used as an effective ingredient in producing the product and the outcome also aided the researchers to introduce or develop new products. Lastly, the culinary and the food industry would benefit from this research for it may introduce and discover new products that can contribute to this industry.

Methodology

Research Design

This research used an experimental data gathering technique, which allows the researchers to test or to do a trial and error process if the arrowroot flour is an effective and efficient way to produce pandesal. The researchers originally planned to have an approval with the Department of Science and Technology regarding the ingredients for the production of arrowroot pandesal. Unfortunately, as the researchers tried to reach them out, there was no response regarding their inquiry about testing the product. In its place, the researchers gathered evidence, references, and resources to justify and prove the study. Upon reaching the findings, it needs to be supported with references from previous researchers or research, either in support or agreement with the findings. They also used web-based nutritional analysis to provide the nutritional content of the product, Arrowroot Pandesal.

Sample

The trained laboratory panel and the expert sensory panel were both used as panels for this study. They were chosen in advance based on their good health, time availability, and avoidance of arrowroot or flour allergies. The researchers conducted a first orientation session where panelists were given a comprehensive understanding of the descriptive organoleptic approach and an overview of the arrowroot pandesal.

A. Trained Laboratory Panel

To take part in the sensory analysis of food samples, four faculty from St. Dominic College of Asia, Cavite, were invited. These professors possess a National Certificate II (NC II) in commercial cooking, which is given by Technical Education and Skills Development Authority (TESDA) to individuals who have proven their proficiency in every unit of competency required to qualify in commercial cookery. They were chosen because they have expertise in food preparation and production. They were categorized as "trained laboratory panels," who are trained individuals with specific sensory capabilities who engage in a test group.

B. Expert Sensory Panel

As expert sensory panel, five Cavite chefs were chosen as a convenience sample. It is assumed that they had more formal education on what to examine for in an arrowroot pandesal sample in terms of the preparation, presentation, general appearance, color, aroma, texture, and taste.

For the sampling procedure, the researchers used cluster sampling to group them according to the specification.

Instruments

The Research Adviser granted permission for this study to be carried out. The dean of St. Dominic College of Asia's School of International Hospitality and Tourism Management also gave authorization to conduct sensory tests on experts and professional evaluators. Members of the target panel provided their voluntary and informed permission before the approval was issued. Participants in this trial were divided into expert and trained laboratory panelists. Sensory evaluation was conducted from May 26 to June 2, 2021.

Data Collection

This study developed an arrowroot pandesal that utilized arrowroot flour. The process involved baking the developed sample. This study examines the acceptability of the developed arrowroot pandesal.

Ingredients

The following are the ingredients and procedure in the production of arrowroot pandesal:

Table 1. Ingredients of arrowroot pandesal

Ingredients	Formulations (grams)
Instant yeast	4 g
Brown sugar	25 g
Fresh milk	40 g
Water	40 g
Egg	
Butter	30 g
Salt	2 g
Arrowroot flour	50 g
Bread flour	150 g
Breadcrumbs	

Sensory Evaluation

By using arrowroot flour, sensory evaluation was used to determine the level of the panel members' acceptance of the arrowroot pandesal. Between May 26 and June 2, 2021, two distinct sensory panels were conducted.

Members of the panel received instructions prior to the sensory assessment of food samples. The experimental process and directions for completing the score card were described by the investigator. The sensory evaluation of the prepared recipes was performed. A trained panel of four culinary teachers and five specialists used a seven-point hedonic scale to assess sensory quality.

Food samples were served using clean, sanitized utensils. Individual samples were served and were coded with numbers. Individual food samples from the experimental groups were offered. Each of the participants evaluated the sensory attributes of the developed arrowroot pandesal using arrowroot flour.

An adequate number of samples in uniformly sized and shaped white glass containers were provided to the panel at room temperature. An environment that was perfect for testing was maintained during the examination by keeping it quiet and odor-free.

Each panelist received a score card and was tasked with rating the samples according to a range of criteria (general appearance, color, texture, aroma, taste, and overall acceptability). For evaluating foods, the fundamental sensory method was applied. The sensory qualities and general acceptability of each of the meal samples were evaluated using a hedonic test. The sensory evaluation and overall acceptability assessment of the coded food samples were conducted using a 7-point hedonic scale. The categories are transformed into ratings that range from 1 to 7. This scale is represented as: 7 – Very Good; 6 – Moderately Good; 5 – Good; 4 – Fair; 3 – Very Fair; 2 – Poor; and 1 – Very Poor.

Data Analysis Procedure

For descriptive variables, frequency counts, weighted means, and percentages were employed. T-test and F-statistics were used to analyze the data. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to see if there were any significant differences in the food samples in terms of general appearance, color, texture, taste, nutrient content, and overall acceptability. The sensory characteristics and overall acceptability of pandesal made with arrowroot flour were rated by two groups of panelists, and a T-test was employed to see if there was a statistically significant difference between their assessments. Significance will be accepted at a 5% level.

Figure 1. Process flow chart in the preparation of arrowroot pandesal

Table 2. Product costing

Recipe Name: Arrowroot Pandesal

Yield: 10 pcs.

Ingredients	Quantity	Unit Cost	X	Amount
Arrowroot Flour	75 g	345/1000 g=0.345	75 g	25.875
Bread Flour	225 g	40/1000 g=0.04	225 g	9
Sugar	50 g	55/1000 g=0.055	50 g	2.75
Water	60 ml	85/10,000 ml=0.0058	60 ml	0.35
Milk	60 ml	80/1000 ml=0.08	60 ml	4.8
Butter	57 g	44/200 g=0.22	57 g	12.54
Yeast	8 g	40/500 g=0.08	8 g	0.64
Salt	3 g	15/140 g=0.1071428	3 g	0.32
Breadcrumbs	40 g	10/80 g=0.125	40 g	5
Egg	50 g			6
Total				Php 67.275
Expenses:		Php 67.275		
Yield:		10 pcs		
SRP:		Php 12.783 per piece		
Profit:		Php 60.55		

= Php 67.275 (Expenses) X .90 (markup) = 60.55
 = 67.275+60.55 = Php127.83
 = Php 127.83 / 10 pcs = Php12.783 (SRP)
 = Php 12.783 x 10 pcs = 127.83-67.275 = Php60.55 – Profit

Results

Subjects or Respondents of the Study

Subjects or respondents of the study

Figure 2. Ratio of the respondents

Figure 5 displays the subjects or the respondents of the study. The participants were Trained Laboratory Panelists with a total of 44% (4 subjects), while the other portion were Expert Panelists with a total of 56% (5 subjects).

Visual Representation of Data Based on Sensory Evaluation

The data presented are formulated based on the following statement of the problem: What are the sensory characteristics of the developed baked product (pandesal) using arrowroot flour?

APPEARANCE

Figure 3. Sensory evaluation rating on general appearance

It can be gleaned from Figure 6 that among the nine participants involved in the study says that arrowroot pandesal based on its appearance, four people (44.4%) marked it as moderately acceptable, four people (44.4%) said that it is slightly acceptable, and only one person (11.2%) decided that it is neither acceptable nor unacceptable.

COLOR

Figure 4. Sensory evaluation rating on color

In terms of color, Figure 4 indicates that among the nine participants involved, only one person (11.1%) picked it as highly acceptable, three people (33.3%) chose it as moderately acceptable, four people (44.4%) marked it as slightly acceptable, and another one person (11.2%) decided that it is slightly unacceptable.

AROMA

Figure 5. Sensory evaluation rating on aroma

Figure 5 indicates that in terms of aroma, out of nine participants involved in the study, two people (22.2%) chose it as highly acceptable, two people (22.2%) marked it as moderately acceptable, two people (22.2%) said that it is slightly acceptable, one (1) person (11.2%) decided that it is neither acceptable or unacceptable, and two people (22.2%) decided that it is slightly unacceptable.

TEXTURE

Figure 6. Sensory evaluation rating on texture

Figure 6 indicates that among the nine participants involved in the study, only one person (11.1%) decided that it is moderately acceptable, three people (33.3%) chose it as slightly acceptable, four people (44.4%) marked it as neither acceptable or unacceptable, and only one person (11.2%) decided that it is slightly unacceptable.

TASTE

Figure 7. Sensory evaluation rating on taste

As regard to taste, it can be noted in the figure above that among the nine participants involved in the study, four people (44.4%) chose it as moderately acceptable, one person (11.2%) decided that it is slightly acceptable, two people (22.2%) picked it as neither acceptable or unacceptable, and one person (11.2%) marked it as slightly unacceptable.

Level of Acceptability of Sensory Characteristics

Table 3. Level of acceptability of sensory characteristics rated by trained personnel

Characteristics	Arrowroot		Traditional	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
Appearance	5.75	Moderately Acceptable	6.75	Highly Acceptable
Color	5.25	Slightly Acceptable	7.00	Highly Acceptable
Aroma	5.25	Slightly Acceptable	6.00	Moderately Acceptable
Texture	4.25	Neither Acceptable nor Unacceptable	7.00	Highly Acceptable
Taste	5.00	Slightly Acceptable	7.00	Highly Acceptable
Acceptability	5.50	Moderately Acceptable	7.00	Highly Acceptable

Table 3 shows the sensory characteristics and the overall acceptability rating of arrowroot and traditional pandesal. The group of trained personnel rated the overall acceptability of Arrowroot pandesal at 5.17, which indicates slightly acceptable, while the traditional pandesal was rated at 6.79, which indicates highly acceptable.

Table 4. Level of acceptability of sensory characteristics rated by expert personnel

Characteristics	Arrowroot		Traditional	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
Appearance	5.0	Slightly Acceptable	6.4	Moderately Acceptable
Color	5.4	Slightly Acceptable	6.6	Highly Acceptable
Aroma	5.0	Slightly Acceptable	5.8	Moderately Acceptable
Texture	4.6	Slightly Acceptable	6.2	Moderately Acceptable
Taste	5.2	Slightly Acceptable	6.2	Moderately Acceptable
Acceptability	5.2	Slightly Acceptable	6.4	Moderately Acceptable

For the second group of panelists, which are the expert personnel, they rated the overall acceptability of the arrowroot pandesal 5.06, which is slightly acceptable, and the traditional pandesal 6.27, which is moderately acceptable.

Table 5. Test of difference in the sensory characteristics of the developed pandesal

Source of Variation	SS	Df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	478.668	3	159.556	1.147	0.355	3.098
Within Groups	2783.042	20	139.152			
Total	3261.710	23				

According to the accumulated data and results, it is true that there is no significant difference between the sensory characteristics of arrowroot pandesal and traditional pandesal. This means that the null hypothesis was accepted.

Table 6. Summary test of difference

Variable	Statistics	Computed value	Critical value	Interpretation
Sensory characteristics and acceptability	t-test	0.419	2.228	No significant difference

According to the accumulated data and results, it is true that there is no significant difference between the ratings of the two groups of panelists such as: a) trained panelists (culinary instructors), and b) experts (chefs) with regard to sensory characteristics and overall acceptability of the developed arrowroot pandesal prepared with arrowroot flour. This means that the null hypothesis was accepted.

Discussion

The present study aimed to determine the effectiveness of using arrowroot flour for the development and acceptability rate of healthy baked products, particularly arrowroot pandesal. This research also looked into the differences between Arrowroot pandesal and traditional or local pandesal. It was graded on a 7-point hedonic scale based on its sensory characteristics, which included appearance, aroma, texture, taste, color, and overall acceptability. Since the researchers had two sets of panelists, they also aimed to know if there was a significant difference between their evaluations.

Based on the results accumulated, it was found that there is no significant difference in the sensory evaluation between the arrowroot pandesal and the traditional pandesal, as well as in the ratings of the two set panelists concerning its overall acceptability. Most of the ratings were slightly acceptable and moderately acceptable.

However, the researchers also discovered that it is not possible to develop an arrowroot pandesal by using arrowroot flour itself as a basic ingredient. In the first pilot testing, the researchers used a traditional pandesal recipe and just replaced the flour with arrowroot flour. While mixing the wet and dry ingredients, it is impossible to create a loaf using this flour. It was so difficult to incorporate with one another; the dough was so hard it did not rise even though the researchers rested it for about 30 minutes, and also it was actually difficult to portion and shape because it was too sticky. The outcome of the first test was like a cookie; it was flat, crispy, and at the same time chewy. In the second test, they tried 50% bread flour and 50% arrowroot flour. This time it was easier to mix the wet and dry ingredients. The researchers were able to knead it, rest it for 45 minutes, and watch it rise. The outcome was good; the appearance and aroma were good, but the texture was too crumbly, the color was too pale, and the taste did not taste like a traditional pandesal. Thus, they kept on improving the ingredients and process to get what they wanted to achieve.

Apparently, this experiment shows that it is possible to develop a baked product from arrowroot flour. Most of the ratings for arrowroot pandesal were slightly acceptable, which was a good indication that it can be accepted by the trained and expert personnel, but there were factors that were challenging for us to consider, and that was the opinion of the consumer, which can also be a credible response for the improvement of the product.

Although the researchers achieved its aims, there were unavoidable limitations. First, the researchers conducted a small-scale population study. Second, they were not able to conduct a survey of the consumers, which was also considered as a group of people who will benefit from this study. Third, the researchers were not able to do an in-depth study about the nutritional value of arrowroot and traditional pandesal.

Conclusions

This study aimed to develop a healthy baked product by experimental research using arrowroot flour and test its acceptability rate. The researchers considered having two sets of respondents, which were the trained and the expert personnel. Both of the groups were credible and knowledgeable about the study. They also used a survey questionnaire as their research instrument, and it was evaluated through mean score, T-test, and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). Based on the revealed findings, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. What are the sensory characteristics of the developed baked product (pandesal) using arrowroot flour terms of the following:

- General appearance was rated moderately acceptable by the group of Trained Personnel while it was rated slightly acceptable by the Expert Personnel.
- Color was rated slightly acceptable by both of the groups. It was too pale in color as compared to the usual pandesal.

- Aroma was rated slightly acceptable by both of the groups.
- Texture was rated Neither Acceptable nor Unacceptable by the trained personnel and slightly acceptable by the Expert Personnel. It was not soft and too crumbly as compared to the usual pandesal.
- Taste was rated slightly acceptable by both of the groups.

2. Is there a significant difference in the sensory characteristics of the developed pandesal prepared using arrowroot flour as compared to the Traditional Pandesal?

Based on the result, it was proven that there is no significant difference between the sensory characteristics developed in arrowroot pandesal as compared to the traditional pandesal.

3. Is there a significant difference in the ratings of the two groups of panelist such as: a) trained panelists (culinary instructors), and b) experts (chefs) with regard to sensory characteristics and overall acceptability of the developed pandesal prepared with arrowroot flour as compared to the traditional Pandesal?

Based on the result, it was proven that there is no significant difference between the ratings of the two different panels with regards to the sensory characteristics evaluation and the overall acceptability of the developed arrowroot pandesal and the traditional pandesal.

Recommendations

Based on the foregoing findings and conclusions, the following recommendations were offered:

- Future researchers may conduct a survey on a larger size of population for better and more credible results.
- Future researchers may administer an in-depth study about the nutritional content of the arrowroot pandesal.
- Future researchers may improve the sensory characteristics of the arrowroot pandesal itself. They may also conduct a series of testing and evaluations; this is to improve the quality of the arrowroot pandesal until it develops the same or even better sensory characteristics over the traditional pandesal.

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